

Article

Maximizing Reducing Potential of Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles for Efficient Removal of Cr(VI) in Drinking Water

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Abstract

The dimensions and the reduction capacity of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are considered to be the key parameters in achieving the successful, efficient removal of hexavalent chromium, aiming for drinking water purification. This research study focuses on the optimization of reaction parameters during the oxidative precipitation of FeSO₄ carried out in a microwave-heated plug-flow reactor, to realize the preparation of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with an increased reduction potential as reflected in the Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ ratio by approximating the ideal value of 0.5. In particular, the coupling of synthesis with features that allow for control of the oxidation extent, and include the addition of a reducing agent, an increase in ageing temperature, and inhibition of aggregation, were tested as potential approaches to tune the reducing potential and overcome reported Cr(VI) capture efficiencies provided by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles. The evaluation results showed that adding a reductant after nanoparticle formation inhibits spontaneous surface oxidation, bringing an improvement in the Cr(VI) uptake capacity for a residual concentration equal to the new EU regulation limit, by around 40%, reaching a value of 2.15 mg/g. However, working at an ageing temperature of around 100 °C resulted in an even better performance with an uptake increase of 120% and a capacity value of 3.45 mg/g. Finally, adding nanoparticles in the form of a dispersion instead of a dried powder provides an extra 10% improvement as a consequence of limited aggregation.

Keywords: magnetite nanoparticles; synthesis; reduction; water treatment; hexavalent chromium

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1. Introduction

The adoption of methodologies based on the use of nanoparticles have revolutionized drinking water treatment strategies, offering new opportunities for the removal of a wide range of pollutants [1–3]. Their efficiency is primarily related to the extremely high specific surface area, which enables a high density of available sites for interaction with the pollutant's units and the enhanced reactivity of specific phases [4]. Additionally, other physical properties of nanoparticles can be utilized to support their performance (photocatalysis) or assist with their post-separation process (magnetic capture) [5–8]. The separation of used nanoparticles from the purified water stream should be considered to be an equally important task in the process design. Suggestively, with respect to the large quantities

of nanoparticles that should be removed in full-scale systems, the cost of particle separation may become the dominant factor if a typical nanofiltration step is applied. Magnetic nanoparticles, consisting of iron oxides in the majority of the reported cases, represent a very popular class of nanomaterials qualified for water treatment purposes according to their efficiency against multiple pollutants or their introduction as magnetic responding carriers for other active phases [9,10]. Importantly, they also offer the opportunity to overcome the issue of nanoparticle recovery by applying a magnetic separation scheme at the end of the process. Among this class of nanoparticles, magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles have been introduced for the removal of hexavalent chromium. Their reducing potential is initiated by the stabilization of Fe^{2+} ions into their crystal structure, which serve as electron donors that assist the transformation of the highly toxic Cr(VI) species to insoluble Cr(III) ones [11].

Previous studies have indicated that the efficiency of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles in this process is mainly defined by the high availability of Fe^{2+} on the surface and the inhibition of oxidation mechanisms during nanoparticle synthesis and storage. The ratio of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} represents an index of the reducing capacity of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, which combined with their dimensions and the specific surface area, contribute to the observed performance, especially when low residual concentrations are targeted [12]. For instance, an uptake capacity of 2.1 mg/g has been reported at a residual concentration equal to the recently applied regulation limit of 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ in the European Union countries [13], with 44 nm Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ at around 0.45 [14]. Control of the Fe^{2+} percentage is partially achieved by tuning the synthesis pH during the oxidative precipitation method, and as a consequence, the size and the aggregation extent of the formed nanoparticles [15]. Identifying the mechanism of Cr(VI) capture by the Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles using advanced X-ray absorption studies has also verified the important role of maintaining the Fe^{2+} site density on the surface at a high level, with this being the key parameter in improving the competitiveness of such nanoadsorbents [16,17].

Unfortunately, achieving $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratios that are close to the stoichiometric value of 0.5 is a difficult task to fulfil using typical low-cost and high-output synthesis methods such as iron salt precipitation, unless strict inert conditions are offered during production, drying, and storage [18]. The last option is usually accompanied by a significant rise in cost, while it results only in a short extension of the operational lifetime upon exposure to natural water conditions. In addition, it is normally expected that the deviation in the stoichiometry will be amplified on the surface layer, where interaction with Cr(VI) oxyions takes place, especially when the nanomaterial is dried, suggesting that an efficiency drop may occur even for relatively high average $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratios [19]. Therefore, combined susceptibility of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles to oxidation, together with the localized passivation, contribute to the restriction of both the uptake potential and competitiveness of the relevant water purification technology [20].

In the quest to develop a cost-effective procedure for the synthesis of oxidation-resistant Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, this study examines different approaches for the modification of the oxidative precipitation method, aiming for an improvement in the Fe^{2+} percentage level, inhibition of surface oxidation, and overall, enhancement of the Cr(VI) uptake efficiency under realistic water treatment conditions. The key idea was to intervene in the mechanisms of crystal growth and the spontaneous surface oxidation in a way that favors the formation of long-term, chemically stabilized Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles overcoming the oxidation-derived loss of performance observed in previous studies. Such context was examined by establishing a controllable oxidation–reduction equilibrium during both synthesis and application, modifying the chemical environment and the ageing conditions. In particular, the determination of a highly reducing environment during or after

precipitation by the addition of hydrazine, and the increase in ageing temperature by introducing ethylene glycol as a solvent, were examined. Furthermore, the application of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles in an aqueous dispersion instead of a dried form was tested as an additional option to minimize exposure in air and avoid aggregation effects, providing more efficient interaction with the pollutant oxygens.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Reagents

Iron (II) sulfate heptahydrate ($\geq 99\%$, FeSO₄·7H₂O), sodium hydroxide (pellets, $>98\%$, NaOH), sodium nitrate ($\geq 99\%$, NaNO₃), hydrazine monohydrochloride (97%, NH₂NH₂·HCl), and ethylene glycol ($\geq 99\%$, EG) were purchased from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany), while ethanol absolute ($\geq 99.5\%$) was purchased from VWR (Radnor, PA, USA). All chemicals were used as received without further purification.

2.2. Synthesis

Ferrimagnetic magnetite nanoparticles were synthesized by modifying the parameters of the microwave-assisted oxidative precipitation of FeSO₄ operating in a continuous-flow mode as previously reported [21,22]. The preparation involved the formation of green rust by the reaction of a 0.1 M FeSO₄ solution in 0.01 M H₂SO₄, with a mixture of NaOH (0.22 M) and NaNO₃ (0.1 M) in ethanol/water (1:6), into a 0.4 L continuous-stirring tank reactor (CSTR) operating with a residence time of 20 min. Using a peristaltic pump, outflowing green rust was directed into a microwave-heated plug-flow reactor where the temperature of the dispersion reached 90 °C for a residence period of 70 s to achieve ageing and transformation of the green rust into Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles. Ageing took place in a Telemax 20MX79 microwave heater (Thessaloniki, Greece) with an output power up to 700 W and a frequency of 2450 MHz. The establishment of reducing conditions was achieved in the following three ways: (i) through the addition of hydrazine solution (0.5–5% *w/v*) during green rust production, or (ii) after the thermal ageing process, and (iii) the replacement of part of the water by EG as a solvent (57–86%), to increase the ageing temperature up to 130 °C (Figure 1). Since using hydrazine monohydrochloride initiated acidic hydrolysis and a drop in pH depending on its concentration, the pH of the green rust or the formed nanoparticles dispersions was adjusted to the alkaline range by adding drops of a 0.1 NaOH solution. The obtained Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles were magnetically separated from the reaction mixture and then, washed several times with distilled water to remove any residual reagents. Finally, they were kept as a concentrated aqueous dispersion or dried at environmental conditions and sieved below 63 μm. The list of synthesized nanoparticles and the main preparation parameters are summarized in Table 1. It should be clarified that the concept of using hydrazine as a reducing reagent in this study aimed only to evaluate performance when synthesis takes place in an environment with the highest possible reducing potential, and a very fast reaction rate leaving no interfering residuals. However, due to the health and environmental issues related with hydrazine's handling, other less toxic reducing agents or the control of stoichiometry should be considered for practical industrial scale-up.

Figure 1. Schematic of the continuous-flow production of highly reducing Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles using various options to control oxidative activity.

Table 1. Synthesis parameters and main characteristics of the obtained nanoparticles.

Sample	Final pH	N_2H_2 (% w/v)	EG (% v/v)	Ageing Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Crystal Size (nm)	$\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}_{\text{theor}}$ (%)
Option 1: Reductant addition before ageing						
1	4	1	-	90	18.1	54.9
2	9.5	1	-	90	21.0	88.7
3	9.5	5	-	90	37.5	93.6
Option 2: Reductant addition after ageing						
4	4	1	-	90	26.4	91.9
5	9.5	1	-	90	31.6	104.5
6	9.5	5	-	90	30.1	149.3
Option 3: Ageing temperature elevation						
7	9.5	-	57	100	24.9	109.0
8	9.5	-	71	105	25.8	109.8
9	9.5	-	83	120	24.3	131.1
10	9.5	-	86	130	8.4	73.7
Reference	9.5	-	-	90	36.2	59.8

2.3. Characterization

The examination of the main crystal structures of the samples were examined by X-ray diffractometry (XRD) using a water-cooled Rigaku Ultima Plus instrument (Tokyo, Japan) operating at 40 kV and 30 mA with CuK α radiation, a step size of 0.05° , and a step time of 2 s. Crystal phases were identified after comparison to the Powder Diffraction Files (PDF) database [23]. The crystallite size (L) of nanoparticles was determined by

applying the Scherrer equation to the major peaks $L = K \cdot \lambda / \beta \cdot \cos\theta$, with K being a shape factor taken equal to 0.9, λ the wavelength of the X-ray radiation, i.e., 0.15406 nm, β the full-width half maximum in rad, and θ the Bragg angle. The morphological features and the localized chemical composition were determined by field-emission gun environmental scanning electron microscopy (FEG-ESEM) with a QUANTA FEI 200 microscope (Hillsboro, OR, USA) operating with accelerating voltage at 30 kV, equipped with an EDAX electron dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analytical system.

The $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratio was determined by quantifying the Fe^{2+} and the total Fe percentage in dried nanoparticles. In this way, the percentage ratio of Fe^{2+} compared to the ideal for the stoichiometric Fe_3O_4 ($\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}_{\text{theor}}$) was also extracted. First, the Fe^{2+} concentration was measured after acid digestion of 0.1 g of the sample under heating with 50 mL of 7 M H_2SO_4 and the colorimetric titration with a 0.05 M KMnO_4 solution dropped by an automatic burette. The end point was defined by the appearance of a weak pink color. The accuracy of the method was confirmed by using a reference sample of ferrous ammonium sulfate, whereas each titration was repeated three times, ensuring a percentage error below 2%. Total iron, and therefore Fe^{3+} , was determined by graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrophotometry using a PerkinElmer AAnalyst 800 (Springfield, IL, USA), after sample dissolution in HCl (accuracy < 3%).

2.4. Cr(VI) Capture

The potential improvement in the efficiency of the developed Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles to remove Cr(VI) was evaluated through batch adsorption experiments and the plotting of adsorption isotherms in concentration ranges that indicate the potential to fulfil the upcoming EU regulation limit of 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$. Experiments involved the 24 h equilibration of a weighted quantity of nanoparticles with a Cr(VI) test solution prepared into challenge water with a similar composition to typical groundwater, as suggested by the National Sanitation Foundation (NSF) standard [24]. In particular, the natural-like challenge water was prepared by the dissolution of 2.52 g (30 mmol) NaHCO_3 , 0.1214 g (1.4 mmol) NaNO_3 , 0.0018 g (0.0013 mmol) $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.0221 g (0.53 mmol) NaF, 0.706 mg (3.7 mmol) $\text{NaSiO}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.47 g (10 mmol) $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 1.283 g (5.2 mmol) $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, in 10 L of distilled water. Test Cr(VI) solutions with varying concentrations of 50–5000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ were prepared by spiking a proper volume of a 100 mg/L stock solution in the natural-like test water. Then, 20–100 mg of nanoparticles were dispersed into 200 mL of aqueous Cr(VI) solution placed in 300 mL conical flasks. Dispersions were shaken for 24 h at 20 °C on an orbital shaker, regulating the pH to a value of 7, and then, the solid was separated by filtration through 0.22 μm pore-size membranes. The residual Cr(VI) concentration was determined by the diphenylcarbazide colorimetric method using a UV–visible spectrophotometer (Hitachi U-5100, Hitachi, Tokyo, Japan) adjusted at a wavelength of 540 nm. The addition of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles was carried out in dried fine powder, but also in the form of a concentrated aqueous dispersion, to test any positive effect of lower exposure to air and avoiding aggregation occurring during the drying process.

The obtained adsorption isotherms were fitted by the Freundlich function:

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n} \quad (1)$$

where q_e is the amount of Cr(VI) captured per mass of adsorbent, C_e the equilibrium concentration, and K_F and n are constants related to adsorption capacity and affinity, respectively. The Langmuir function was also used:

$$q_e = \frac{K_L q_{\max} C_e}{1 + K_L C_e} \quad (2)$$

with K_L representing the Langmuir affinity constant and q_{max} representing the maximum adsorption capacity.

Kinetic data were obtained by equilibrating 250 mg/L of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles (dispersed or dried) in a Cr(VI) solution of 1 mg/L and sampling at various time intervals up to 48 h. For the thermodynamic investigation of the uptake process, the isotherms were additionally recorded at temperatures of 5 and 35 °C.

3. Results and Discussion

XRD diagrams were taken to confirm the presence of the magnetite's inverse spinel structure in the produced nanoparticles (Figure 2). The results indicate that all samples exhibit very similar characteristics concerning the dominant crystal structure, since the obtained peaks comply with the expected diffraction lines of the Fe_3O_4 . Since crystallographic discrimination of the Fe_3O_4 structure from the $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ one is difficult, results from the manganometry determination of Fe^{2+} content were used to assist the identification of the major constituent phase in each sample (Table 1). The addition of hydrazine with other reagents before thermal ageing seems to inhibit crystal growth in an acidic environment, as revealed by the relatively low mean crystal size, and enhance surface oxidation to $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ as soon as $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ hardly overcomes half of the Fe_3O_4 stoichiometry value. Adjustment of the pH to the alkaline range enables higher $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ values approaching stoichiometry values when 5% hydrazine solution is added. In parallel, the mean crystal size significantly increases up to around 37.5 nm.

Figure 2. XRD diagrams of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles synthesized under reducing environment before (pre- N_2H_2) and after (post- N_2H_2) ageing, or at higher ageing temperatures defined by EG addition. Inset on the top is a magnification of pointed areas in the diagrams corresponding to the samples with the highest $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}_{\text{theor}}$ ratios. Box inset is a magnification of the 2theta range where weak peaks corresponding to the FeO structure were identified.

Introducing the hydrazine solution in the formed nanoparticle dispersion appears to be a more convenient approach to achieve higher reducing activity and stabilize the maximum Fe^{2+} percentage while avoiding any interference in the growth stage. Near-stoichiometry ratios were obtained even when precipitation took place at acidic conditions, whereas increases in both crystal size, up to around 31.5 nm, and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ were observed in an alkaline environment. Importantly, the Fe^{2+} ratio of around 150% was comparable to the theoretical value for Fe_3O_4 , which was determined for the sample prepared with 5% hydrazine, suggests that an overdose of reducing agent may oppose partial oxidation of ferrous ions and stabilize small quantities of less oxidized forms of iron oxides, probably located in the core of nanoparticles, such as wüstite (FeO), which is evidenced by weak peaks in the XRD diagram (inset Figure 2). A similar trend is observed for the samples synthesized under elevated ageing temperatures, defined by the gradual ethylene glycol addition. The crystal size fluctuates around 25 nm for all samples prepared up to 120 °C but suddenly drops below 10 nm during ageing at 130 °C, when ethylene glycol actually replaces most of the water with the solvent. The simultaneous decrease in Fe^{2+} percentage much below the over-stoichiometry value observed for ageing temperatures below 120 °C, indicates a sudden interruption of particle growth with the deficiency of water, becoming more susceptible to surface oxidation. A possible reason for this observation is the transition of the synthesis reaction from an aqueous precipitation procedure to a polyol process. In particular, the ionic-controlled mechanism that occurs in the first case is defined by parameters such as the acidity and the surface charge, whereas when higher ethylene glycol percentages are used, kinetic and reaction yield are negatively affected by the significant modification of solubility, dielectric constant, viscosity, capping, and complexation effects.

The morphological features of representative samples for each case are presented in the SEM images of Figure 3. In agreement with the low mean crystal size determined by the XRD analysis, an average diameter of 22.3 ± 5 nm was measured by the electron microscopy images when the pre-addition process of hydrazine was followed (Figure 3a), indicating that interference of the growth step by the reductant not only inhibited the crystal growth but the building up of the whole nanoparticle as well. On the other hand, post-addition of hydrazine is accompanied by a larger diameter of 36.3 ± 3 nm (Figure 3b), suggesting that the growth of nanoparticles is uninterrupted and hydrazine only acts as a guarding agent against oxidation at the end of the process. Working at elevated temperatures shows a gradual decreasing trend concerning the average particles dimensions, as observed for those prepared at 100 °C (Figure 3c) and those at 120 °C (Figure 3d), which have a mean diameter of 29.1 ± 3 nm and 24.8 ± 4 nm, respectively. Considering the identical crystal size values of the samples up to the ageing temperature of 120 °C, it appears that heating energy favors the formation of monocrystalline nanoparticles.

The effect of the synthesis conditions and the obtained morphological and chemical characteristics of studied Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles in the Cr(VI) capture performance were evaluated through the corresponding uptake isotherms. Figure 4 presents the isotherms for the Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles collected by the application of oxidative precipitation in the presence or the post-addition of hydrazine. The results are compared with the efficiency of a reference sample prepared by the oxidative precipitation in the absence of hydrazine. From the uptake isotherms of samples prepared with hydrazine, it is clear that without pH adjustment to the alkaline region, the efficiency of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles significantly decreases. However, an improvement is observed when synthesis takes place at pH 9.5, with slightly better performance to be measured for the higher hydrazine dose addition (5%).

Figure 3. SEM images of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles synthesized at $90\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and alkaline conditions by adding 1% hydrazine before (a) and after (b) ageing, or by adjusting ageing temperatures at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (c) and $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (d) by EG addition.

Data points of uptake isotherms were plotted using the Langmuir and Freundlich models, with the parametrization results shown in Table 2. The Freundlich approximation, which assumes heterogeneity of uptake sites on the nanoparticles and multilayer capture of the pollutant, provides more accurate fitting in all cases. By using such an equation, the uptake capacity (Q_{25} value) that provides a residual concentration of Cr(VI) equal to the regulation limit of $25\text{ }\mu\text{g/L}$ for the EU was estimated. Accordingly, the Q_{25} for the pre-addition of 5% hydrazine was calculated to be 1.8 mg/g , i.e., almost 15% better than that of the reference Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, which showed a capacity of 1.55 mg/g . In the case of 5% hydrazine post-addition in the formed nanoparticles, Q_{25} reaches 2.15 mg/g , achieving an improvement of around 40%.

Figure 4. Isotherms for Cr(VI) uptake by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles synthesized at 90 °C by adding hydrazine before (a) and after (b) ageing. Corresponding data for the reference sample prepared without hydrazine addition are also given for comparison. Plotted lines represent the Freundlich-type fitting.

Table 2. Parameters of Langmuir and Freundlich models applied in the uptake isotherms.

Sample	K_L (L/ μg_{Cr})	q_{max} (mg $_{\text{Cr}}$ /g)	R^2	K_F (μg_{Cr} /mg)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$) ^{1/n}	1/n	R^2
Option 1: Reductant addition before ageing						
1	0.0039	4.1433	0.9952	0.0770	0.5882	0.9784
2	0.0251	3.6958	0.9942	0.6304	0.2885	0.9870
3	0.0330	3.7362	0.9711	0.7619	0.2651	0.9968
Option 2: Reductant addition after ageing						
4	0.0373	2.3230	0.9646	0.5207	0.2516	0.9984
5	0.0509	3.4471	0.8915	0.8183	0.2460	0.9984
6	0.1037	3.4663	0.8426	1.1554	0.1962	0.9947
Dispersed	0.0885	4.9389	0.8998	1.1288	0.2298	0.9897
Option 3: Ageing temperature elevation						
7	0.0903	3.0490	0.8243	1.0140	0.1939	0.9547
8	0.1457	3.6927	0.9660	1.4567	0.1689	0.9785
9	0.0872	4.5302	0.9021	1.2461	0.2320	0.9990
Dispersed	0.0231	7.0730	0.8710	1.4762	0.2162	0.9985
10	0.0560	6.5524	0.9260	1.4210	0.2752	0.9827
Reference	0.0362	3.1660	0.9518	0.7233	0.2449	0.9985
Dispersed	0.0056	5.6584	0.9053	0.6206	0.2914	0.9982

However, instead of using a reducing agent, increasing the ageing temperature appears to be a more efficient way of improving the uptake capacity, as observed by the plotted isotherms of Figure 5. Working at 100 °C outperforms all other tested cases by far, giving a significant rise in Cr(VI) uptake compared to the reference sample. Higher ageing temperatures also show an improvement in Cr(VI) reduction, which follows a decreasing trend with the temperature level, or else with the substitution extent of water by EG. Freundlich fitting of the data was also used to estimate the Q_{25} values of samples synthesized with EG addition. Importantly, introducing EG percentages up to around 70% *v/v* results in Q_{25} values of up to 3.45 mg/g for an ageing temperature of 100 °C, representing an increase of 120% in comparison to the reference sample. Larger ageing temperatures are accompanied by a drop in Q_{25} to 2.6 mg/g for 105 °C and an approximation of the reference's efficiency for 130 °C.

Having tested the options of reducing agent addition and ageing temperature increase during Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle synthesis to improve the efficiency for Cr(VI) capture, the preservation of particles dispersed in water instead of their addition in dried form was attempted, aiming to minimize the aggregation effect and loss of specific surface area. Figure 6 presents the uptake isotherms of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles prepared by the post-addition of 5% hydrazine at an ageing temperature of 105 °C, but kept in a dispersion form. In addition, the corresponding measurement for the reference sample was plotted. For comparison, the determined Freundlich curves for the samples tested in dried form are also introduced in the diagram. The results indicate an obvious enhancement of the uptake capacity when the quantity of nanoparticles is introduced by a concentrated aqueous dispersion, for all cases. The sample synthesized at 105 °C achieves a Q_{25} value of 2.9 mg/g, showing an increase of around 12% in comparison to the powder addition case, and overall, it performs almost 90% better than the reference sample. The corresponding change for the nanoparticles prepared by the post-addition of 5% hydrazine brings around a 7% enhancement to the dried sample and around 50% compared to the reference.

Figure 5. Isotherms for Cr(VI) uptake by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles synthesized at various temperatures by adding EG. Corresponding data for the reference sample prepared without EG addition are also given for comparison. Plotted lines represent the Freundlich-type fitting.

Figure 6. Isotherms for Cr(VI) uptake by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles synthesized at 90 °C by post-addition of 5% hydrazine and ageing at 105 °C by adding EG, added in the form of aqueous dispersion (point-curve diagrams) in comparison to the case of dry fine powder addition (similar-color dashed curves). Corresponding data for the reference sample prepared are also given for comparison. Plotted lines represent the Freundlich-type fitting.

An overview of the estimated Q_{25} values for the studied samples at an equilibrium pH 7 is given in the bar diagram of Figure 7. It can be determined that the addition of hydrazine at the end of thermal ageing process and adjustment of the pH of green rust to the alkaline region are more favorable in achieving a significant improvement in efficiency. Uptake performance is also proportional to the concentration of the reducing agent, as verified by the higher Q_{25} values for the 5% solutions. However, modification of the ageing temperature to higher values by EG addition provides a better potential to achieve even doubling of the efficiency, whereas introducing nanoparticles from a dispersion rather than dried powder gives an extra enhancement. Apart from the significant improvement for the specific synthesis method, the measured Q_{25} values are classified among the highest ever reported for Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles. For instance, 30 nm nanoparticles prepared by the co-precipitation of iron salts in a continuous-flow reactor showed a capacity of around 1.8 mg/g for residual Cr(VI) levels at 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$ [18]; meanwhile, when applied as aggregates in rapid small-scale column tests, the Q_{25} value was even higher, reaching 4 mg/g at pH 7 [25]. Increasing the diameter of nanoparticles (~ 80 nm) resulted in a large drop in performance below 1 mg/g [26], signifying the importance of the specific surface area in the reduction-assisted uptake process. Several other studies testing iron oxide nanoparticles (Fe_3O_4 , $\gamma\text{-}Fe_2O_3$) have indicated efficiencies worth mentioning; however, the extremely low pH values and the Cr(VI) concentration ranges suggest their applicability only for wastewater treatment [27–33]. Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles developed in this study provide Cr(VI) uptake performance competitive to phases with a higher reducing potential including zero-valent iron (ZVI) nanoparticles and the tin oxyhydroxide nanostructures. ZVI supported on carbon, silica, or humus have shown Q_{25} values in the range of 8–118 mg/g, although reported results correspond to the pH range of 5 and the matrix was distilled water [34–36]. More compatible with the conditions of evaluation is the case of bivalent Sn oxyhydroxide, which achieves an uptake capacity of 7 mg/g, though the higher production cost should be considered [37].

Figure 7. Cr(VI) uptake capacity values by studied Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles corresponding to a residual concentration of 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Q_{25}).

Working at pH 7 was selected as a typical condition met in an average water sample oriented for drinking purposes. Nevertheless, it should be mentioned that variations in the water pH in the range of 6–8 may affect the observed Q_{25} values by a significant increase when moving to lower values and a decrease under more alkaline conditions, as described in a previous study [25]. Such observation is related to the increase in negative surface charge as pH moves away from the isoelectric point of Fe_3O_4 (around 6.5), while Cr(VI) speciation indicates CrO_4^{2-} as being the dominant form versus HCrO_4^- in the same region [18]. Additionally, the interfering potential of common ions found in natural water resources has been illustrated for the case of Cr(VI) uptake by Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, suggesting a decrease in efficiency by more than 50% compared to experiments carried out using distilled water. Separate investigations for each interfering ion indicate a weak interference by Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and HCO_3^- ions ranging from 0 to 20% at extremely high concentrations of up to 0.01 M, and a more significant negative effect by SiO_3^- and PO_4^{3-} that may approach 50%, though in non-realistic concentrations.

Since slightly increasing the ageing temperature by the addition of EG appears to bring the highest efficiency gain, an estimation of the expected synthesis cost increase is also provided. The techno-economic analysis of the laboratory-scale microwave-assisted synthesis of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles indicated that reagents and labor cost are the major expenses, whereas energy consumption contributes a small percentage owing to the fast microwave heating procedure [21]. Therefore, replacement of water by EG is estimated to add around a 5% inelastic cost for the production and around an extra 2% of the expenses for the waste treatment unless some method to recycle the EG/water mixture is adopted. In total, the profit of almost doubling the efficiency in Cr(VI) is sufficient to overcome the production cost elevation, which is expected to be around 10%.

To understand the uptake mechanism and the time-dependence of its stages, kinetic data were collected for the sample synthesized by the post-addition of 5% hydrazine and that aged at 105 °C by EG addition. Corresponding curves for the addition of nanoparticles in the form of an aqueous dispersion are provided for comparison. The results were plotted by correlating the uptake capacity with the square root of time, as shown in Figure 8, to clearly indicate the two linear regions and the change in slope, which corresponds to the transition from the initial rapid step to the equilibrium state and brings a slower capture till saturation. Interparticle diffusion appears to be the rate-determining step mechanism, suggesting the capture of Cr(VI) oxyions on the surface porous of the nanoparticles. Such a process lasts for around 3 h for all samples, with a slightly faster approach for the case of nanoparticle addition as a dispersion. Dispersed nanoparticles also allow significantly higher equilibrium uptake capacities than dried ones. At the equilibrium state, X-ray absorption and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy analysis studies on similar Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles provided evidence for the electron exchange mechanism, which causes the precipitation of Cr(III) and the gradual passivation of Fe^{2+} on the particle surface [12,18,38].

Although the required time to fully reach the maximum capacity of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles appears to be long, from a practical point of view, in a continuous-flow application process, the residence time can be tuned to be much more reasonable and flexible depending on the flowrates of the purification unit, as explained in the design of an integrated Cr(VI) uptake and magnetic separation setup [7]. In addition, proper design of the separator has been shown to be more than sufficient to support complete recovery of the nanosized solid, as evidenced by the absence of solid or dissolved Fe in the outflowing stream of the magnetic separator.

Figure 8. Kinetic data of Cr(VI) uptake capacity values by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles synthesized at 90 °C by post-addition of 5% hydrazine and ageing at 105 °C by adding EG, added in the form of aqueous dispersion (full circles) in comparison to the case of dry fine powder addition (open circles). Dotted vertical line indicates the time of transition.

The data of kinetic experiments were better fitted by a pseudo-second order equation [39]:

$$q = \frac{k_2 q_e^2 t}{1 + k_2 q_e t} \tag{3}$$

with t being the time in min, k_2 the kinetic constant, and q_e the uptake capacity at equilibrium. Fitting parameters are summarized in Table 3 for the studied cases.

Table 3. Parameters of pseudo-second order fitting of kinetic data.

Sample	k_2 (g/mg _{Cr} min)	q_e (mg _{Cr} /g)	R^2
5% N ₂ H ₂ post-addition	0.0039	3.278	0.9593
Dispersed	0.0035	3.758	0.9541
EG 105 °C	0.0031	4.383	0.9864
Dispersed	0.0037	4.988	0.9841

The temperature dependence of Cr(VI) uptake was studied for the same representative samples by plotting the isotherms for experiments carried out at 5 and 35 °C, in addition to that for 20 °C, extended to higher residual concentrations (Figure 9). For the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles prepared with hydrazine addition at the end of ageing, the capacity values

appear to slightly increase with temperature (Figure 9a). However, the isotherm shift to higher capacities is stronger for the sample synthesized at 105 °C (Figure 9b). Experimental data were fitted by a Langmuir equation and the obtained parameters, shown in Table 4, were used to estimate the thermodynamic values such as the free energy ΔG , the entropy ΔS , and the enthalpy ΔH .

Figure 9. Extended isotherms for Cr(VI) uptake by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles synthesized at 90 °C by post-addition of 5% hydrazine (a) and ageing at 105 °C by adding EG (b), at temperatures 5, 20, and 35 °C. Plotted lines represent the Langmuir-type fitting.

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters derived from isotherms in the range 5–35 °C.

Sample	K_L (L/ μg_{Cr})	q_{max} ($\text{mg}_{\text{Cr}}/\text{g}$)	R^2	$-\Delta G^{\circ}$ (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (J/mol K)	ΔH° (kJ/mol)
5% N ₂ H ₂ post-addition						
5 °C	0.0086	3.5536	0.9762	14.1	270.1	60.2
20 °C	0.1037	3.4663	0.8426	20.9		
35 °C	0.1040	3.8955	0.8746	22.0		
EG 105 °C						
5 °C	0.0019	7.3225	0.9677	10.6	269.8	64.2
20 °C	0.0110	6.8381	0.8065	15.5		
35 °C	0.0280	7.4248	0.8988	18.7		

First, the ΔG° value was calculated according to the following equation [40,41]:

$$\Delta G^{\circ} = -RT \ln K_L, \quad (4)$$

with R being the gas constant, which is equal to 8.314 J/(mol·K), and T being the temperature in Kelvin units. The negative values suggest that Cr(VI) uptake by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles is spontaneous and thermodynamically feasible, while there is a tendency for a mechanism increase to occur at higher temperatures. The ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated by fitting ΔG° values in the following equation:

$$\ln K_L = -\frac{\Delta H^{\circ}}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S^{\circ}}{R} \quad (5)$$

The obtained enthalpy and entropy were almost identical for the two studied cases, indicating no significant difference in the thermodynamic features of the Cr(VI) uptake process introduced by the variation in dimensions and iron oxidation ratio. Positive values of entropy imply to the enhancement of the random configuration in the solid–liquid interface. This is possibly related to the displacement of ordered water molecules from the iron oxide surface when Cr(VI) oxyions are initially adsorbed, while the release of hydroxyls or sulfates after ion exchange with Cr(VI) oxyions also contributes to the enhancement of randomness. On the other hand, positive enthalpy corresponds to the endothermic nature of the process since Cr(VI) by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles is favorable at higher temperatures. The overall endothermic process result from the dehydration step of Cr(VI) oxyions taking place just before the initial adsorption, the reduction reaction between Fe²⁺ and Cr(VI), which requires higher activation energy as a chemical transformation, and the requirement for site activation (Fe²⁺ ions in the structure). In addition, a rising uptake capacity at higher temperatures should be partially attributed to the increase in water viscosity, which enables an easier approach of Cr(VI) oxyions to the particle surface.

After saturation, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are surface-passivated meaning that captured Cr has been introduced in the crystal structure while Fe²⁺ are fully oxidized to Fe³⁺. According to this, potential regeneration requires removal of the Cr solid precipitate and partial reduction of Fe³⁺ to the Fe²⁺ state. The only way to realize that is by rebuilding Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles via the following methods: (1) complete dissolution of the nanoparticles by an acid, (2) precipitation of the Cr as a separate product, and (3) finally, re-precipitation of dissolved Fe to obtain new Fe₃O₄. Obviously, this procedure is associated with a higher cost than direct particle synthesis, though upon careful design, it can be demonstrated to be a circular economy solution [42].

4. Conclusions

The combination of a low synthesis cost, high availability, and controllable morphological characteristics have promoted Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles obtained from oxidative precipitation to being a favorable adsorbent for water purification toward Cr(VI) removal. This study indicated the existence of further possibilities to improve their performance by featuring the synthesis and handling of the product with different approaches that minimize surface oxidation and particle aggregation effects without a significant impact on the cost. In particular, introducing a typical reductant such as hydrazine at the end of the growth process appears to act as a guard to inhibit surface oxidation and stabilize a high Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ ratio able to enhance Cr(VI) uptake capacity by a factor of 1.4. Alternatively, slightly increasing the ageing temperature by 10–20 °C, by replacing water with EG, facilitates an even higher efficiency increase. This almost doubles the Q₂₅ value for the sample prepared using the typical method, almost reaching 3.5 mg/g, which appears to be a significant upgrade for this class of nanomaterials. Finally, an additional 10% upgrade is introduced when nanoparticles are stored and applied in the form of a concentrated aqueous dispersion instead of a dried powder. Such a possibility becomes feasible according to the main advantage of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles related to their magnetic response and easy separation. Further research should be carried out to overcome the limitations of this study related to the use of hydrazine by its replacement with other less harmful reductant candidates, whereas the impact of synthesis temperature and solvent exchange should be analyzed concerning the impact on cost and the environment.

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